

A HISTORICAL OVERVIEW OF ECOLOGY AND ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION IN UZBEKISTAN

**Shukhrat Eshonqulovich Toshturov, Doctoral Candidate
Navoi State University, Navoi city, Uzbekistan**

On January 11, 2017, in Davos, Switzerland, the World Economic Forum released the "Global Risks Report 2017," which emphasized that ecological and geopolitical challenges pose significant threats to humanity in the 21st century [1]. In the "Global Risks Report 2017" published on January 11, 2017, in Davos, Switzerland, experts identified 13 trends among 30 global risks that could intensify or evolve. Among the most significant threats, three pertain to ecology and three to geopolitics, with environmental risks ranked as the highest priority. Indeed, at the dawn of the third millennium, experts began referring to the 21st century as the "Century of the Environment." According to their data, human activity influences 90% of natural processes occurring on Earth. During the era of "human civilization," characterized by economic development, two-thirds of the planet's forests have been cut down, 250 species of animals and plants have become extinct, 3 to 4 billion hectares of land have been removed from agricultural use, and the oxygen reserves in the atmosphere have decreased by 10 billion tons [2].

Today, the global environmental catastrophe has not bypassed Uzbekistan. In the 1950s and 1960s, efforts to expand agricultural lands and reclaim millions of hectares of virgin territories began to yield bitter consequences by the 1980s. During this period, the degradation of the environment in our country was also caused by the excessive use of various toxic chemicals, mineral fertilizers, and similar substances in agriculture. For instance, during the Soviet era, more than 50 kilograms of toxic chemicals were applied per hectare annually, placing Uzbekistan among the leading republics in the Soviet Union in this regard [3].

In Uzbekistan, environmental protection efforts began in 1920 with the establishment of the Committee for the Protection of Museums, Art, and Natural Monuments of Turkestan. In 1959, to promote the establishment and rational use of protective forests and to safeguard soil, plants, animals, and atmospheric air, the Department of Forestry and Environmental Protection was created. This department was based on the Forestry and Field Protective Afforestation Inspectorate and the Hunting Department of the Ministry of Agriculture of the Uzbek SSR. By the early 1960s, the need for environmental protection in Uzbekistan had intensified, and issues concerning nature conservation began attracting greater public attention. As a result, in 1961, the Society for the Protection of Nature was established in Uzbekistan. In 1963, the Department for the Protection of Nature and the Earth's Resources was created under the Supreme Soviet of the Uzbek SSR. During the 1970s, the increase in environmental pollution in industrial cities and mining regions, along with growing water resource shortages, led to the emergence of several urgent ecological problems. Beginning in 1978, the responsibility for conducting research on these issues and monitoring environmental pollution was assigned to the Hydro-Meteorological Service of the Uzbek SSR. Finally, in 1988, the State Committee for Nature Protection of the Uzbek SSR was established [4].

Following the attainment of state independence, Uzbekistan faced the necessity of addressing environmental issues inherited from the Soviet era. This included the development of a healthy ecosystem, the formulation of its scientific foundations, and the implementation of practical measures. To this end, a legal framework for resolving environmental problems was established in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Nearly 40 laws and approximately 1,000 subordinate legal acts were adopted concerning environmental protection and the rational use

of natural resources. Notably, in recent years, more than 30 significant laws and around 150 subordinate legal acts have been enacted, focusing on public health, environmental protection, sustainable utilization of natural resources, and ensuring national environmental security [5]. As a result of the effective measures being implemented in our country in the field of ecology and environmental protection, the level of impact on nature is being reduced.

On January 8, 2019, the Ecological Party of Uzbekistan was established to address political processes related to ecology, a priority area for the state and society, focusing on natural resource conservation and environmental protection [6]. On May 31, 2023, the Ministry of Ecology, Environmental Protection, and Climate Change was established to develop and implement a unified state policy in Uzbekistan regarding environmental protection, rational use of natural resources, their restoration, waste management, and climate change [7]. Currently, various state and non-governmental organizations are actively engaged in environmental protection, rational use of natural resources, and the implementation of laws and regulations pertaining to these areas. Their efforts focus on ensuring environmental cleanliness, safeguarding public health, organizing greening initiatives, enhancing public participation, and promoting ecological culture.

In conclusion, following Uzbekistan's independence, it became imperative to address ecological issues inherited from the Soviet era, such as the utilization of land and water resources, loss of biodiversity, and environmental pollution, along with their social consequences. Consequently, the establishment of the Ministry of Ecology, Environmental Protection, and Climate Change enabled the state to address these environmental problems and monitor the enforcement of related legal documents at the national level. In summary, a legislative system dedicated to environmental protection has been established in our country. The most crucial aspect now is the practical implementation and enforcement of these laws and regulatory documents.

References

1. https://www3.weforum.org/docs/GRR17_Report_web.pdf
2. Holmuminov Zh.T., Shoimov N.B., Kamalov O.A., Holmuminov O.J. "Environmental Law." – Tashkent: Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2014. – pp. 9–10.
3. Alibekov, L. Human and Nature. – Tashkent: Fan va Texnologiya, 2016. – p. 5.
4. Holmuminov, J. Ecology and Law. – Tashkent: Adolat Publishing House, 2000. – pp. 31–33.
5. Ibragimov, N.A. Institutional and Functional Integration of the Environmental Security System. Abstract of the Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) dissertation in Philosophy. – Tashkent, 2019. – p.14.
6. Ecological Party of Uzbekistan. Five Steps Towards a Green Future [Text]: Articles / Ecological Party of Uzbekistan. – Tashkent: Ijod NASHR Publishing House, 2024. – p.10.
7. <https://lex.uz/uz/docs/6479134?ONDATE=06.01.2024>